

THE IMPACTS OF COVID-19 ON THE TOUR GUIDING IN AEGEAN REGION*

COVID-19'UN EGE BÖLGESİ'NDE TUR REHBERLİĞİNE ETKİLERİ

Ferika Özer SARI

Assoc. Prof. Dr., Yaşar University, School of Applied Sciences, Dep. of Tourism Guidance, İzmir, Türkiye, ferika.ozersri@yasar.edu.tr ORCID- 0000-0001-9899-256X

Yaşar Can AY

Yaşar Can AY, yasar-canay@hotmail.com, Mugla, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

The pandemic has affected humanity very seriously. Many sectors have stopped or minimized their operations because the pandemic has been bringing some necessities to prevent the spread of the virus. One of the most affected sectors by Covid-19 disease is tourism industry. Services in many areas of tourism such as transportation, food and beverages, accommodation and entertainment have come to a standstill. This study aims to reveal the impacts of Covid-19 and identify the factor structure of tourist guides' perceptions related to the effects of this pandemic on their profession. Tourist guides in the Aegean region were reached through an e-survey within the scope of obtaining information about their perceptions. There are 2260 tourist guides from "Aydın Chamber of Tourist Guide", "Muğla Chamber of Tourist Guide" and lastly "İzmir Chamber of Tourist Guide" in the Aegean region. In this context, it is reached, 183 tourist guides from the 1564 active tourist guide. Answers from the tour guides were analyzed via the SPSS computer program. In line with these data analyses, the factor structure is created and suggestions are listed.

Key Words: Covid-19 Pandemic, Tourism, Tourist Guides' Perceptions in Aegean Region

ÖZET

Covid-19 pandemisi tüm insanlığı ciddi bir biçimde etkilemiştir. Pandemi, virüsün yayılmasını önlemek için bazı zorunlulukları beraberinde getirdiği için birçok sektör durma noktasına yaklaşmıştır. Covid-19 hastalığından en çok etkilenen sektörlerden biri de turizm sektörü olmuştur. Ulaşım, yeme-içme, konaklama ve eğlence gibi turizmin birçok alanındaki hizmetler büyük oranda kısıtlanmıştır. Bu çalışma, Covid-19'un etkilerini ortaya koymayı ve turist rehberlerinin bu pandeminin meslekleri üzerindeki etkilerine ilişkin algılarının faktör yapısını belirlemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Ege bölgesindeki turist rehberlerine, e-anket aracılığıyla ulaşılmıştır. Ege bölgesinde "Aydın Turist Rehberleri Odası", "Muğla Turist Rehberleri Odası" ve son olarak "İzmir Turist Rehberleri Odası"na kayıtlı 2260 turist rehberi bulunmaktadır. Bu kapsamda 1564 aktif turist rehberinden 183 turist rehberine ulaşılmıştır. Tur rehberlerinden gelen cevaplar SPSS programı ile analiz edilmiştir. Bu veri analizleri doğrultusunda faktör yapısı oluşturulmuş ve çeşitli önerilerde bulunulmuştur.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Covid-19 Pandemisi, Turizm, Ege Bölgesi Turist Rehberlerinin Pandemi Algısı

1.INTRODUCTION

Due to the deferrable structure of tourism activities, tourism industry was between the top sectors to be affected by the COVID-19 pandemic (Çetin and Göktepe, 2020, p. 90). Tourism is one of the most important socio-economic factors in creating employment at tourist destinations (Abbas et al., 2021, p. 2). During the pandemic, governments' decisions like restrictions such as prohibitions of public areas and transportation caused the tourism industry to take a pause (Saraç, 2020, p. 122).

Figure 1. demonstrates the International Tourist Arrivals' Rates between 2019 and July 2021 (UNWTO, 2021a). Generally, while decreases occurred in 2020 at -73%, this rate of arrivals was -80% in the first seven months of 2021. Additionally, drop rates of the America continent are the same in both 2020 and 2021 but in the other continents, decreases can be observed within the first seven

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months of 2021. According to UNWTO (2021a), the drop rate of the first seven months of 2021 is below as 40% compared to 2020. This rate equals to 147 million tourists (UNWTO, 2021b, p. 1).

Figure 1. International Tourist Arrivals' Rates (UNWTO, 2021a).

According to IATA (2021), passenger-kilometer revenue decreased by 66% in 2020 in airline industry. ICAO (2021), declared that the airline industry had 371 billion dollar revenue losses in 2020. In this regard, the pandemic has directly affected tour guides in tourism industry. Tourist's needs and motivations have started to change with the beginning of the pandemic. People began to care their health in the pandemic (Mbatha et al., 2021, p. 1463). Especially, tour guides could not perform their primary role, which is interacting with tourists in person (Galí, 2022, p. 2).

2. COVID-19 AND TURKIYE

Türkiye is affected by the Covid-19 pandemic as economically. Especially, some sectors that importantly contribute to Türkiye's economy, such as tourism, take damage from the pandemic. The economic contribution that tourism makes to Türkiye's GDP was 77, 6 billion dollars at 11% of total GDP in 2019 but in 2020, this contribution fell down to 35, 5 billion dollars at 5% of the total GDP of Türkiye (WTTC, 2021).

According to WHO (2021), there had 8,921,150 million confirmed cases in Türkiye from 3 January 2020 to 7 December 2021 and the Covid-19 death number reached approximately 78 thousand. On the other hand, 120,114,498 million doses of vaccines were done in Türkiye as of 30 November 2021 (WHO, 2021). After the pandemic, dismissals and seasonal closures of tourism businesses in Türkiye, affected the tourism industry seriously because of quarantines, curfews, closing of borders and international travel restrictions (Kervankıran and Bağmancı, 2021, p. 264). According to Association of Turkish Travel Agencies (TÜRSAB, 2020), there is a loss of 120 thousand employment in Türkiye because of these issues (p. 20).

Turkey Ministry of Culture & Tourism (2021) prepared a journal that is mentioned numbers of tourists coming to Türkiye by years. In 2019, the number of tourists coming to the country increased by 14%, to correspond 45 million tourists and for 2020, it was aimed to reach 50 million tourists (Kervankıran and Bağmancı, 2020, p. 20; TÜRSAB, 2020, p. 17). In April and May 2020, the number of visitors

decreased and there were issues such as suspension of international flights, closing of borders, restrictions and quarantines over 90% of cities in Türkiye because of intensifying of the pandemic (Kervankıran and Bağmancı, 2020, p. 20). That is why there is a decrease from April 2020 over 90% (Kervankıran and Bağmancı, 2021, p. 264). According to TÜRSAB (2020), there was 72, 5% decrease in 2020 compared to previous years in visitor numbers (p. 18). According to data of Turkey Ministry of Culture & Tourism (2021), total visitor numbers in Türkiye are 45 million in 2019, approximately 13 million in 2020 and 21 million in 2021. There were decreases in April and May 2020 by -99% (Turkey Ministry of Culture & Tourism, 2021; UNWTO, 2021c). On the other hand, September 2020 had the highest number of visitors with 2,203,482 and the rate between 2019 and 2020 has been just -59% (Turkey Ministry of Culture & Tourism, 2021; UNWTO, 2021c). In 2021, numbers closed to 2019 data. Especially, on October 2021, the numbers of visitors are very close to the same month of 2019 (Turkey Ministry of Culture & Tourism, 2021; UNWTO, 2021c). In addition to these, the number of people who travel from Türkiye to abroad, decreased over 70% (Kervankıran and Bağmancı, 2021, p. 265).

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, a quantitative research technique is used for collecting data. Quantitative analysis is collecting and gathering research answers with numerical data (Mohajan, 2018, p. 3). In this direction, the survey method is used as the primary data collection tool. Analysis were operationalized via the SPSS program.

3.1. Aim of the Study

Tourism guidance is one of the most important sectors affected by Covid-19 pandemic because the guides interact intensely with tourists during the tours. Nowadays, bad incidents like wars and diseases can affect the tourism and the tourism guidance profession. In this context, the aim of this study is to understand and identify the factor structure of tourist guides' perceptions related to the effects of Covid-19 pandemics on their profession.

3.2. Scale Development

The scale of the survey is created in many processes and statements of the scale are inspired from the literature. In the questions, which are related to socio-demographic questions in the survey, the statement that is "Tourism Guidance Education" is adapted from "Distribution of the tourist guides according to whether or not receive tourism education" (Yazıcıoğlu, Tokmak and Uzun, 2008, p. 7). The statement that is "Guidance Time (Year)" is adapted from "Work Experience (Year)" (Özkan and Yeşildağ, 2021, p. 1607). The statement that is "Cockade Type" is adapted completely same from "Distribution of the tourist guides according to the cockade type which they have" (Yazıcıoğlu, Tokmak and Uzun, 2008, p. 8). Additionally, the statement that is "How long after the pandemic ends, will tourism return to its former version?" is adapted from "Tourism Effect Prediction of the Pandemic Process" (Türker and Karaca, 2020, p.8). Lastly, the statement that is "I have participated in more than 20 tours from the beginning of 2020 until today" are adapted from "The Number of the Tours From the Beginning of the Pandemic to the Date of Research Which is Made" (Özkan and Yeşildağ, 2021, p. 1608).

In the second part of the survey that is "During the Pandemic", some questions are also adapted from some research. The statement that is "During the pandemic, there has been an economic loss in tourism." is adapted from "What are your solution suggestions for the economic losses which occurred or may occur possibly in the tourism sector because of the Covid-19?" (Düzgün and Kurt, 2020, p. 24). The statement that is "Many people who I know in the tourism industry, have experienced unemployment issues." is adapted from "In the pandemic period, travel agencies, tour

operators...” (Özkan and Yeşildağ, 2021, p. 1605). The item that is “I was affected in a bad way as both financially and morally during the quarantine and curfews in the pandemic.” is adapted from “Guides who have to earn money on tour to survive...” (Düzgün and Kurt, 2020, p.31). Another item which is “During the pandemic, I have needed to do another job except tourism guidance.” is adapted from “Do you think to do another profession after the Covid-19 pandemic?” (Düzgün and Kurt, 2020, p. 24); “I received informative training about Covid-19 by state organizations.” is adapted from “What Association of Tourist Guides and Trade Associations should do, Free Online Educations” (Türker and Karaca, 2020, p.9) and “I have been having anxiety because of the Covid-19 while going on tours.” is adapted from “Do you feel safe towards Covid-19 in the period that you work?” (Düzgün and Kurt, 2020, p. 24). Lastly, the statement that is “Repayment loan support for tourist guides was insufficient.” is adapted from “Guides were able to benefit in the lower levels...” (Düzgün and Kurt, 2020, p.32).

In the third part of the survey that is “After the Pandemic”, the statement that is “After the pandemic, tourists will start to demand tourism products mostly from digital environments.” is adapted from “Organizations which are like national and international meeting, conference...” (Kıvılcım, 2020, p.23); “At the end of the pandemic, grants should be given to tourist guides.” is adapted from “Ministry Precautions, Grant Support” (Türker and Karaca, 2020, p.9); “There will be changes in tourists’ behaviors and their travel habits when the pandemic ends.” is adapted from “What kind of changes may occur in holiday and travel preferences of the tourists when the life returns to normal in the post-pandemic according to your opinion?” (Türker and Karaca, 2020, p. 6). The item that is “There will be changes in the tourism guidance profession” is adapted from “What do you think about how the tourist guide profession will be shaped in the post-pandemic?” (Türker and Karaca, 2020, p. 6). Lastly, the statement that is “Even if a new pandemic or disease does not appear after the pandemic, we will observe digitalization movements in the tourism industry.” is adapted from “It is possible to say that there will be pass to digital age...” (Kıvılcım, 2020, p.25).

Before sharing the survey with all participants, the pilot study was applied to 31 tourist guides in the Aegean region via e-mail. When checking out the statements, there were 20 statements in the “During the Pandemic” survey and 18 statements in the “After the Pandemic” survey. According to the results, some statements were excluded in both surveys because of inconsistency. The statements “1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 16 and 20” were removed from the first “During the Pandemic” survey. Statements “10, 11 and 17” were removed from the second “After the Pandemic” survey. After removing some questions from the survey, 0, 84 Cronbach’s Alpha score and 0, 72 KMO and Barlett’s test scores are reached in the second part of the survey. On the other hand, 0, 94 Cronbach’s Alpha score and 0, 82 KMO and Bartlett’s test scores are reached in the last part of the survey. After reaching these compatible results, the survey is shared with all tourist guides in the Aegean region.

3.3. Research Population and Sampling

The population of the research consists of active tourist guides in the Aegean Region. In the region, there are three “Chambers of Tourist Guide”s which are ATRO, which is located in Kusadasi, IZRO, which is located in Izmir, and lastly MUTRO, which is located in Mugla.

According to the website of Association of Tourist Guides (TUREB, 2022), there are totally 11770 tourist guides in Türkiye and there are 2314 tourist guides in Aegean Region. The number of people actively doing the guidance profession is 8142 guides in Türkiye and 1564 in Aegean Region (TUREB, 2022). In this context, 1564 questionnaires were sent and 183 surveys are collected via both electronic way and face-to-face in small amounts because of the Covid-19 pandemic.

3.4. Data Collection

Surveys are sent to tourist guides by e-mail, face-to-face and mail of chambers of tourist guides and social media channels. All information about the survey are given to guides before sharing the survey with them. Survey has three sections. In the first section, socio-demographic questions are asked to the participants. The total questions of these are 13. In this part, questions were asked about gender, ages, education level, chamber of the guide, Covid-19 and experiences in guiding. In the second part of the survey, there are 13 5-Likert scale questions about tourism guides' situations during the pandemic. Answers consist of 1 to 5. Starting from one, there are options such as Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Unstable (3), Agree (4), Strongly Agree (5). In the last part of the survey, there is another 5-Likert scale same as the second part of the survey, but the topic is related to tour guides' situations after the pandemic.

4. FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The survey was answered by 183 tourist guides, which are from Aydın, İzmir and Muğla provinces. According to the results, participants include mostly males with 120 participants out of 183. When the findings regarding the age of the participants are examined, "50 and more" age participants equal to 36, 6 % of participants (n=67).

When the findings regarding the education level of participants are examined, bachelor's degree participants are in the majority with 62, 8 % (n=115). When looking at the tourism guidance education of participants, mostly, participants joined guidance certificate education for being a tourist guide with 40, 4 % (n=74). These guidance certificate educations are prepared sometime in a year by tourism guidance chambers. There are three chambers of tourist guides, which are Aydın, İzmir and Muğla, in the survey. Mostly, İzmir Chamber of Tourist Guides dominates the results of the analysis with 49, 7 % (n=91). The other question is related to guidance year in the profession. Most of the participants, which are equal to 49, 2 % (n=90) have worked 15 and more years in the guiding profession. On the other hand, most of the guides who joined the survey are national guides that can do guidance profession in all Türkiye. Apart from these variables, there are other questions related the Covid-19 in the socio-demographic part. First, when the findings regarding the number of infected people with the virus during the pandemic are examined, most of the participants have never been caught to Covid-19 as 75, 4 % (n=138). In the second part, there are just answers that relate to infected people, except "have never been caught" answers. 20, 8 % of the participants do not know how they are caught the virus (n=38).

When the findings regarding the number of vaccinated participants are examined, nearly all participants are vaccinated at least once except one person. Generally, participants have vaccinated three doses and it represents 48, 1 % of the participants. On the other hand, when the findings related to returning tourism's former version after the pandemic are examined, participants are nearly distributed across all answers normally. 55 participants think that tourism return to its former version within 1 year. In the last part of the demographic questions, there is a question about the number of tour guides participating to tours since the beginning of the pandemic. When checking out the results related to this issue, half of the guides could not join the tour during the pandemic.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N=183)

Variables		N	%
Gender	Female	63	34.4
	Male	120	65.6
Age	20-29	29	15.8
	30-39	58	31.7
	40-49	29	15.8
	50 and more	67	36.6
Education Level	High School	8	4.4
	Associate Degree	25	13.7
	Bachelor Degree	115	62.8
	Graduate Degree	35	19.1
Tourism Guidance Education	Tourism Associate Degree	41	22.4
	Tourism Bachelor Degree	61	33.3
	Tourism Graduate Degree	7	3.8
	Guidance Certificate Education	74	40.4
Chamber of Tourist Guide	Aydın Chamber of Tourist Guides	48	26.2
	İzmir Chamber of Tourist Guides	91	49.7
	Muğla Chamber of Tourist Guides	44	24.0
Guidance Time (Year)	0-4	33	18.0
	5-9	30	16.4
	10-14	30	16.4
	15 and more	90	49.2
Type of Cockade	National	151	82.5
	Regional	32	17.5

Have you caught the Covid-19?	Never Caught	138	75.4
	Been Caught Once	42	23.0
	Been Caught More Than 1	3	1.6
If you got caught, how did you get caught?	Do Not Know	38	20.8
	During Tour	6	3.3
	From My Friends	2	1.1
	From My Family	11	6.0
	From My Relatives	1	0.5
Have you been vaccinated?	Yes	182	99.5
	No	1	0.5
If vaccinated, how many doses?	1 dose	1	0.5
	2 doses	58	31.7
	3 doses	88	48.1
	4 doses	18	9.8
	5 doses or more	17	9.3
How long after the pandemic ends, will tourism return to its former situation?	Before 1 year	42	23.0
	1 year	55	30.1
	2 years	54	29.5
	3 or more years	32	17.5
I have participated in more than 20 tours from the beginning of 2020 until today	Yes	87	47.5
	No	96	52.5

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

In this part, there are descriptive statistics of all statements of the survey. It was asked to answer these statements on a 5-Likert-scale that includes from “Strongly Disagree”, “Disagree”, “Neutral”, “Agree” and lastly “Strongly Agree”, from the participants. In these statements, the highest mean rate is at “During the pandemic, there has been an economic loss in tourism” with 4, 88. “Many people who I know in the tourism industry, have experienced” statement follows it very closely by 4, 73. The lowest rate is at “I received informative training about Covid-19 by state organizations.” by 2, 91.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of the Items

ITEMS	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
During the pandemic, there has been an economic loss in tourism.	183	4,88	,531
During the pandemic, the number of domestic visitors was higher than the number of foreign visitors.	183	4,25	1,012
Many people, who I know in the tourism industry, have experienced unemployment issues.	183	4,73	,662
I was affected in a bad way as both financially and morally during the quarantine and curfews.	183	4,52	,895
During the pandemic, I have needed to do another job except tourism guidance	183	3,90	1,267
I received informative training about Covid-19 by state organizations.	183	2,91	1,354
I have substantially adapted to the rules of "Tourist Guides Pandemic Circular".	183	4,19	1,058
Double doses of vaccines increased tourism movements.	183	3,84	1,179
I have been having anxiety because of the Covid-19 while going on tours.	183	3,75	1,209
Many tourist guides have caught the Covid-19 despite taking precautions.	183	3,72	1,036
Repayment loan support for tourist guides was insufficient.	183	4,51	,943
In the pandemic period, tour agencies have sold tours to customers mostly via internet channels.	183	4,20	,880
In the normalization period, the number of tourists that come to our country increased noticeably.	183	3,33	1,277
Tourism will regain its pre-pandemic performance.	183	3,76	1,128
There will be increases in the amount of foreign currency that enter the country through tourism.	183	3,88	1,108
The interest of foreign and local tourists will increase towards destinations.	183	4,06	,962
The interest of foreign and local tourists will increase towards tours.	183	4,09	,985
The number of long-distance travels will increase in the world.	183	3,96	1,047
Mass tourism activities will increase in the world.	183	3,82	1,165
After the pandemic, tourists will start to demand tourism products mostly from digital environments.	183	3,93	1,017
Employment for tour guiding will increase when the pandemic ends.	183	3,88	1,009
At the end of the pandemic, grants should be given to tourist guides.	183	4,19	1,032
There will be changes in tourists' behaviors and their travel habits when the pandemic ends.	183	4,25	,903
Innovative ideas should be applied to tourism at the end of the pandemic.	183	4,30	,852
Grants should be given to tourism businesses that are in loss or on the verge of the bankruptcy.	183	4,41	,813
There will be changes in the tourism guidance profession after the pandemic.	183	3,87	1,090
Even if a new pandemic or disease does not appear after the pandemic, we will observe digitalization movements in the tourism industry.	183	4,00	,926
There will be an increase in the price of tourism products and services after the pandemic.	183	4,16	,897

4.2. Reliability Analysis

Some analysis was used to measure the reliability of the survey questions. In this context, Cronbach Alpha of the questions was measured to observe their reliabilities. According to Ursachi et al. (2015), 0,60-0,70 Cronbach Alpha scores are acceptable for research, 0,80 and above are greater and lastly, 0,90 and above are excellent for the survey questions (p. 681).

Reliability Analysis of “During the Pandemic” Survey

The Cronbach Alpha score of this survey is 0,747. This score is sufficient for the reliability of the survey’s analysis.

Table 3. Item Correlations of the “During Pandemic Survey”

ITEMS		Corrected Item Total Correlations
Dp1	During the pandemic, there has been an economic loss in tourism.	0.600
Dp2	During the pandemic, the number of domestic visitors was higher than the number of foreign visitors.	0.283
Dp3	Many people, who I know in the tourism industry, have experienced unemployment issues.	0.572
Dp4	I was affected in a bad way as both financially and morally during the quarantine and curfews.	0.484
Dp5	During the pandemic, I have needed to do another job except tourism guidance	0.253
Dp6	I received informative training about Covid-19 by state organizations.	0.184
Dp7	I have substantially adapted to the rules of “Tourist Guides Pandemic Circular”.	0.524
Dp8	Double doses of vaccines increased tourism movements.	0.294
Dp9	I have been having anxiety because of the Covid-19 while going on tours.	0.316
Dp10	Many tourist guides have caught the Covid-19 despite taking precautions.	0.486
Dp11	Repayment loan support for tourist guides was insufficient.	0.526
Dp12	In the pandemic period, tour agencies have sold tours to customers mostly via internet channels.	0.498
Dp13	In the normalization period, the number of tourists that come to our country increased noticeably.	0.256

Reliability Analysis of “After the Pandemic” Survey

The Cronbach Alpha score of the second survey is 0,885. According to Ursachi et al. (2015), this score is nearly perfect for reliability. Nearly, the highest value is obtained without removing questions from the survey.

Table 4. Item Correlations of “After Pandemic Survey”

ITEMS		Corrected Item-Total Correlation
Ap1	Tourism will regain its pre-pandemic performance.	0.632
Ap2	There will be increases in the amount of foreign currency that enter the country through tourism.	0.689
Ap3	The interest of foreign and local tourists will increase towards destinations.	0.747
Ap4	The interest of foreign and local tourists will increase towards tours.	0.728
Ap5	The number of long-distance travels will increase in the world.	0.701
Ap6	Mass tourism activities will increase in the world.	0.648
Ap7	After the pandemic, tourists will start to demand tourism products mostly from digital environments.	0.380
Ap8	Employment for tour guiding will increase when the pandemic ends.	0.608
Ap9	At the end of the pandemic, grants should be given to tourist guides.	0.287
Ap10	There will be changes in tourists' behaviors and their travel habits when the pandemic ends.	0.485
Ap11	Innovative ideas should be applied to tourism at the end of the pandemic.	0.576
Ap12	Grants should be given to tourism businesses that are in loss or on the verge of the bankruptcy.	0.508
Ap13	There will be changes in the tourism guidance profession after the pandemic.	0.400
Ap14	Even if a new pandemic or disease does not appear after the pandemic, we will observe digitalization movements in the tourism industry.	0.431
Ap15	There will be an increase in the price of tourism products and services after the pandemic.	0.417

4.3. Factor Analysis

Factor analysis is multivariate statistics that create a significant few new variables by gathering so many variables that wait to discover (Büyüköztürk, 2002). KMO and Bartlett's Test is necessary for

indicating the suitability of factor analysis. KMO and Bartlett's Test scores are between zero and one generally.

Table 5. KMO and Bartlett's Test of "During the Pandemic Survey"

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		,784
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	649,370
	df	78
	Sig.	<,001

According to Table 5, KMO and Bartlett's Test score of the "During the Pandemic" scale is 0,784. It is very good results for Chan and Idris (2017). "Sig." or the significance value of the scale is below from $p < 0,005$. That is why this scale is very appropriate for the factor analysis.

Table 6. Factor Analysis of "During the Pandemic Survey"

"During the Pandemic" Survey	Factor 1 Economic Impacts	Factor 2 Normalization Process	Factor 3 Virus Impacts During the Tour	Factor 4 Quarantine and Curfew Impacts
Item 2	,901			
Item 3	,815			
Item 1	,634			
Item 11	,624			
Item 12	,413			
Item 8		,794		
Item 13		,767		
Item 7		,610		
Item 6		,533		
Item 9			,864	
Item 10			,752	
Item 5				,885
Item 4				,513
Cumulative % = 60,759	30,909%	12,618%	9,459%	7,773%

In Table 6, 4 factors can be seen. The Promax method is used for the rotation and suppressed small coefficients. According to the table, in the first factor, there are five items loaded. This factor is totally related to "Economic Impacts". The second factor has also the same items as in the first factor. The second factor is related "Normalization Process". In the third factor, there are just two items, which are items 9 and 10, and this factor is related to "Virus Impacts During the Tour". Lastly, the fourth

factor has two items, which are items 4 and 5. This factor is related to “Quarantine and Curfew Impacts”. These four factors explain 60,759 % of the variance. Firstly, factor 1 explains 30,909 % of it. The second factor follows it by 12,618 %. The third factor’s rate is 9,459 %. Finally, the last factor affects to variance as 7,773%.

In the “Economic Impacts” dimension of the “During the Pandemic” survey, the guides had difficulties on unemployment and economic issues during the pandemic. In addition to these, guides think that repayment credits are insufficient in the economic depression during the pandemic. They reported that tourism was affected in every way and had to just serve mostly to domestic tourists rather than foreigners. On the other hand, when checking the “Normalization Process” dimension, guides are in a dilemma about the sufficiency of informative education that is made by state organizations in the pandemic. In another variation, most of the tourist guides think that they abide by the rules of the “Tourist Guides Pandemic Circular”. Again, most of them estimate that tourism movements have increased with the double dose of vaccine in the normalization period. Because of this, tourism movements in the normalization period have increased according to tourist guides.

In the third dimension, “Virus Impacts During the Tour”, again, answers are stacked on all the options, but participants have had anxieties about getting sick by Covid-19 during the tours. Currently, they declare that so many tourist guides have caught a virus during the tours; even they have had some precautions for the virus.

Lastly, when looking at the last dimension, which is “Quarantine and Curfew Impacts”, nearly all tourist guides were affected in a bad way as both financially and morally during the quarantine and curfews in the pandemic. Moreover, most of them were looking for new jobs instead of tourist guidance.

Table 7. KMO and Bartlett’s Test of “After the Pandemic Survey”

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		,874
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1538,620
	df	105
	Sig.	,000

KMO and Bartlett’s Test results are shown in Table 7. According to the table, the KMO of the survey is 0,874. According to Chan and Idris (2017), results greater from the 0, 80 are meritorious for the factor analysis. In the “After the Pandemic” survey, the KMO result is 0,874. Thus, this score is perfect for the factor analysis. The significance value of the survey is below $p < 0,005$. Like in the first survey, this survey is also very appropriate for other analysis.

Table 8. demonstrates the factor analysis of the “After the Pandemic” survey. On the first factor, there are seven variables, which are items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 8. Variables in this factor are related “General Situation of Tourism & Guidance”. Items 7, 10, 11, 13, 14 and 15 are related to “Marketing Tourism” as the second dimension. Finally, there are two items (9 and 12) in the third factor as “Need of Financial Support”.

Table 8. Factor Analysis of “After the Pandemic Survey”

“After the Pandemic” Survey	Factor 1 General Situation of Tourism & Guidance	Factor 2 Marketing tourism	Factor 3 Need of Financial Support
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Item 4	,904		
Item 3	,879		
Item 1	,849		
Item 2	,836		
Item 5	,833		
Item 6	,813		
Item 8	,771		
Item 14		,817	
Item 7		,785	
Item 10		,746	
Item 11		,588	
Item 13		,541	
Item 15		,525	
Item 9			,922
Item 12			,685
Cumulative % = 63,546	40,380 %	15,935 %	7,231 %

In the “General Situation of Tourism & Guidance” factor, many people agree with the statement that tourism will regain pre-pandemic performance after the pandemic. Participants also support ideas of increasing long trips and mass tourism activities worldwide. In the perspective of our country, tourist guides declared that foreign currency amounts and foreign tourists will increase, and these tourists will show more interest to tours that guide prepare.

In the second factor “Marketing Tourism”, it is totally related to digitalization and innovative ideas for tourism. Therefore, tourist guides expect innovative ideas and some changes in the guidance profession and other tourism branches such as the digitalization process. Participants expect also that employment in the tourism guidance profession will increase after the end of the pandemic. At the end of the pandemic, tourist guides expect price increases in tourism products and services for the closing current account deficit in tourism. As a third dimension of tour guides’ perception after a pandemic, it’s been seen that the tourist guides want the grant for themselves because they are damaged economically during the pandemic period; additionally, participants also believe that governments should give grants to tourism businesses in trouble.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The tourism industry has been affected by so many crises since earlier decades; however, it has renovated itself at the end of all the bad situations. Especially, the Covid-19 pandemic that occurred in the first quarter of 2020, has affected tourism industry dramatically. From this point of view, the aim of this study was to understand and identify the factor structure of tourist guides’ perceptions related to the effects of Covid-19 pandemic on their profession. As a result of the “During the

Pandemic” survey analysis, four main dimensions and, with the “After the Pandemic” survey, three dimensions are revealed. Then, the research model seen in Figure 2, is created for the dimensions of tourist guides’ perceptions on Covid-19 impacts on their profession.

Figure 2. Proposed Model for the Dimensions of Tourist Guides’ Perceptions on Covid-19 Impacts

In line with the proposed research model, some suggestions are made, based on the information obtained from Aegean region tourist guides. In order not to have similar experiences in the tourism sector as Covid-19 pandemic, the following points are recommended to be done:

- Aid packages and special loans should be arranged for tourism businesses that cover all subcomponents and all employees in the tourism sector. Especially, some payments should be made to tourist guides who could not work during the pandemic, quarantines and restrictions.
- Countries where tourism is one of the most important income sources can arrange plans for tourism in terms of “preventing the spread of the pandemics” for not to be impacted. It is necessary to act together with the ministries of health to prevent the spread of any viruses through tourism.
- The high level of anxiety of many guides during the tours because of the pandemic creates uncomfortable working conditions for tourist guides. The main reason for that can be

explained with the sharp decrease in the number of tourists and tour programs. In general, this situation forces the tourist guides to find alternative jobs. Thus, various projects that might pull qualified tourist guide candidates should be designed and conducted by the Chambers of Tourist Guides and governments.

- It is known that many informative educations related to the pandemic were uploaded on the website of the Association of Tourist Guides (TUREB). According to the current research participants, tourist guides are in a dilemma about this issue. Based on the guides' answers, informative educations about the pandemic should have been given via online platforms, universities and schools by the state organizations before the pandemic. On the other hand, service quality training programs should be organized for tourist guides, related with first aid Covid-19 and/or any other diseases.
- As new pandemics or diseases may occur around the world, new technologies that might decrease human contact for well-being should be taken seriously in the tourist areas.
- Even the Covid-19 pandemic ends at some day, tourist guides should comply with the rules and circulars, which are prepared by the state organizations.

To conclude, it is known that the majority of the tourists join to the tours, which are prepared and promoted by the tourist guides in the Aegean region. Nevertheless, in order to increase the interest of international tourists on the guided tours, an effective marketing about those tours, besides the country's health policies and precautions should be conducted.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The population of the research was limited because of the Covid-19 pandemic. Thus, research was held only in the Aegean region. On the other hand, the questionnaire was distributed by the internet channels due to the pandemic. Some survey papers were delivered to the chambers of tourist guides because meeting face-to-face is difficult with guides during the pandemic period.

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